

Target CRM	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Dy	Ga	Ba and Sr	Sm + Co	Ta	Ga	Sb	Sb	Sn	Ag, Au, Pd	Co	Sc	W	Cu	
applications/waste flow	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in speakers	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in motors	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in HDD	additive to Nd+Pr magnets for heat resistance	as a minor additive in Nd+Pr permanent magnets	Ferrite permanent magnets in speakers/leds/used	Semiconductors: Cobalt permanent magnets in sensors (rare presence)	in capacitors on PCBs	integrated circuits and microprocessors in PCBs	Rare retarder in PCB resin	in PCB solder	in PCB solder	connector, contact, pins, and plating in PCBs	integrated circuits and microprocessors in PCBs	integrated circuits and microprocessors, thin film applications in PCBs	electron emitter in integrated circuits in PCB	contacts and connectors in PCBs	
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	To capacitors remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; Ta mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	Go/Cu remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	If PCBs are not removed from the device and the whole product gets mechanically treated, Ag, Au, and Pd can get dispersed in dust fraction. PCB parts end up in Cu smelter, or different plastic and residue fractions which go to incineration. Ag, Au, Pd end up in the metal phase as impurity on incineration bottom ash (Eckhardt et al., 2024)	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Cu mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, W mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	If PCBs are not removed from the device and the whole product gets mechanically treated, PCB parts end up in different plastic or residue fractions. Cu remains after incineration in bottom ash flow fraction without further separation		
(Partially) existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling or element recovery (long loop recycling) (purity requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024))	selective removal of PCBs with additional manual or automated removal of Ta capacitors from PCBs or motor metal (Berggren et al., 2022); European Commission, 2026; Planas et al., 2019)	removal of Go/Cu from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Go recovery from concentrates (Eckhardt et al., 2022); European Commission, 2026; Planas et al., 2019)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sb recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelüken, 2006). 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Torge, 2006; Mark & Latwe, 2022)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sb recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelüken, 2006). 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Torge, 2006; Mark & Latwe, 2022)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Sn can be recovered (Hagelüken, 2006)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electrorefining from Cu anode slimes (KAS) (Hagelüken, 2006) (Eckhardt et al., 2024)	theoretical scenario removal of Co-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Co recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of Sc-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Sc recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with W recovery from concentrates	PCBs or parts of PCBs are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Cu is recovered Cu is also recovered when PCBs are not disassembled and Cu parts are removed from a shredded waste flow Cu could be recovered from MSW bottom ash by advanced bottom ash processing	
Nb	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?																
design/input-specific criteria	11 Disruption and heterogeneity in product/waste flow (accumulation and mass fraction within a product/waste flow)	How disrupted is the CRM and/or the CRM containing application in the product? Is the CRM and/or CRM containing application accumulated in specific components? Is the CRM accumulated/shredded in parts of the waste flow or is it more widely distributed within the waste flow? How is the CRM mass fraction in relation to the ore grade (in the application/component/product/parts of the waste flow)?	Nd and Pr are not highly disrupted in the product - they are concentrated in the Nd+Pr magnets. The Nd + Pr content in permanent magnets is typically around 30%. Not all speakers use Nd+Pr magnets, also ferrite magnets are widely used for larger speakers.	Nd and Pr are not highly disrupted in the product - they are concentrated in the Nd+Pr magnets. The Nd + Pr content in permanent magnets is typically around 30%. Not all motors use Nd+Pr magnets, also ferrite magnets or electrochromes are used. Motors in battery driven devices have mostly Nd+Pr magnets.	Nd and Pr are not highly disrupted in the product - they are concentrated in the Nd+Pr magnets. The Nd + Pr content in permanent magnets is typically around 30% (chemistry does not vary a lot). The Nd+Pr magnet in HDDs is always in a corner of the HDD.	Dy is highly found in the Nd+Pr alloy and therefore not highly disrupted in the product, but concentrated in the Nd+Pr magnets. The Dy content can reach up to 6%, with high variations between 0-8% (Lubbenbach & Ruten, 2015). The spindle magnet rotates the disk in HDDs and is located in the middle of it.	Ga is highly found in the Nd+Pr alloy and therefore not highly disrupted in the product, but concentrated in the Nd+Pr magnets. Around 0.5% of Ga is used for magnet doping (Huang et al., 2022). Not all Nd+Pr magnets are doped with Ga, therefore the disruption among products is high.	Ba and Sr are not highly disrupted in the product - they are concentrated in the ferrite magnets. The Ba content in ferrite permanent magnets varies between 0.5% (in strontium ferrites) and 9% (in barium ferrites). The Sr content varies between 0.5% (in barium ferrites) and 9% (in strontium ferrites) (Fulco et al., 2019). Not all speakers use ferrite magnets, also Nd+Pr magnets are used especially in small devices.	Sm and Co are not highly disrupted in the product - they are concentrated in the SmCo magnets. Au/Cu is also used in other applications, it can also be found in other components. There are two alloy types: - SmCo2 (25% Sm, 75% Co) - SmCo5 (36% Sm, 64% Co) (Stanford Magnets, n.d.) SmCo magnets are not widely used and therefore highly disrupted among products.	Ta is concentrated in the surface-invented Ta capacitors on PCBs. The mass fraction of Ta in the capacitor is 48-49%. The mass fraction in relation to the whole PCB is low, 0.4-1% (Eckhardt et al., 2024)	Ag is used as Gallium Arsenide (GaAs) or Gallium Nitride (GaN) semiconductors in ICs on PCBs specifically in power electronics and high-frequency applications, but in low quantities per product and low number of products per waste stream.	Sb is used as flame retardant in the PCB resin. Sb is added as synergist in the form of antimony trioxide (ATO) in combination with halogenated (mainly brominated) flame retardants. (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency, 2015)	Solder is used in small quantities on PCBs to connect different components. Sn is the primary constituent in solder used in all types of PCB and accounts for around 1-5% of the mass of PCBs.	Au is found in contacts of many slits and interfaces. Ag is mostly concentrated in fine lead contacts of electronic components and in microchips. Pd can also be found in contacts of interfaces. All three elements mass fractions are higher than the ore grade. It is reported that the mass percentage of Au, Ag, and Pd in PCBs account for 0.03-0.1, 0.05-0.1, and 0.01-0.1, respectively, which is 10 times more than that of rich minerals (Huang et al., 2022)	Co in ICs is only used for special applications, and in low quantities per component, per product and low number of products.	Sc in ICs is only used for special applications, and in low quantities per component, per product and low number of products.	Very tiny component	Cu is the primary conductor in PCBs and is integrated in the PCB resin as Cu foil, etched Cu tracks and Cu pour.
12 Change in product design/input (changes in quantities, replacements, etc.)	What are the current developments regarding change in product design, quantities and replacements? Are there expected input changes that will affect the waste flow?	There is a trend to miniaturization of magnets and devices resulting in replacement of ferrite magnets with Nd+Pr magnets.	Some high-power magnets (often in automotive motors) get laminated with small epoxy layers. The epoxy acts as an electrical barrier to reduce eddy currents and improve efficiency.	HDDs are more and more replaced by SSDs without permanent magnets especially in removable devices such as laptops. HDDs will still be used in data centers.	HDDs are more and more replaced by SSDs without permanent magnets especially in removable devices such as laptops. HDDs will still be used in data centers.	Research shows Ga doping improves coercivity and thermal stability, enabling better performance with same Nd content, though it is experimental (lab scale) (Huang et al., 2022). Ga content in permanent magnets might therefore increase in the future.	Ferrite magnets are more and more replaced by Nd+Pr magnets due to their better performance especially in devices where small magnets with high strength are needed.	SmCo2 alloy magnets (25% Sm, 75% Co) are more commonly used than SmCo5 alloy magnets (36% Sm, 64% Co) (Stanford Magnets, n.d.). Sensors are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	There is no substitution of Ta with Nb, niobium (Eckhardt et al., 2024)	Gallium ICs (GaAs, GaN) are used in an increasing range of products, but are still in very low quantities relative to total flow.	No changes expected except the trend to non-halogenated flame retardants.	No information	ICs and surface-mount technology reduces the size of PCBs and the use of solder.	Modern electronics use less Au in connectors and PCBs due to improved manufacturing, but high-end devices still have higher quality, connector-resistant components. Au remains essential and unreplaced in critical connections.	No information	No information	Alternatives to tungsten wire filaments are solid-state head-on-board crystals (COBs or SMD) (Nanosystems, 2023).	No changes expected
13 Product information and labeling (Identifiability of CRM containing applications and components)	Does the product labeling provide sufficient information about the mass fraction and location of CRM in the product? Is there a required or voluntary labeling?	Magnet specification is currently only based on magnetic strength not chemistry. Speakers are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	Magnet specification is currently only based on magnetic strength not chemistry. The CRMA Act requires labeling of permanent magnets in electric motors indicating: - the amount of permanent magnets in the product - the types of permanent magnets The label design and implementation is currently under development (until 2026). The data center should contain: - product information - information on weight, location, and chemical composition of the permanent magnets - information regarding removal of the permanent magnets	Magnet specification is currently only based on magnetic strength not chemistry. HDDs are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	Magnet specification is currently only based on magnetic strength not chemistry. HDDs are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	Magnet specification is currently only based on magnetic strength not chemistry. If the product falls under the ones where labeling is required under the CRMA Act, the label will also include chemical composition and therefore indication of Ga content. However, the labeling is currently not planned for all products containing permanent magnets.	Speakers are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	Sensors are not listed among the products that require permanent magnets labeling under the CRMA Act. However, there is a general trend to increase labeling of products including DPP etc.	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	There will be DPPs for PCBs (CEN-CENELEC, 2024).	
14 Waste stream-specific criteria	11 Disruption in waste flow	How high is the mass fraction of the CRM in the (collected) waste flow in relation to the ore grade? How is the CRM containing application collected (e.g. application - component - product-level, mixed with other products)? Is there a pre-sorting of components or products? Is there a pre-sorting regarding input materials/parts of the waste flow?	Permanent magnets are typically not dismantled from WEEE. Products with different magnet types are mixed.	Permanent magnets are typically not dismantled from WEEE. Products with different magnet types are mixed.	HDDs are often removed from the device, but permanent magnets are not separated and get shredded together with the HDD for data security reasons.	HDDs are often removed from the device, but permanent magnets are not separated and get shredded together with the HDD for data security reasons.	Permanent magnets are typically not dismantled from WEEE. Products with different magnet types are mixed.	Permanent magnets are typically not dismantled from WEEE. Products with different magnet types are mixed.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	PCBs from small IT and laptops are often shredded and collected separately due to their high value. PCBs in other small and large household equipment are usually not removed. ICs are only used in a small number of products.	
22 Mineralogical state	In which mineralogical state is the CRM in the application or waste flow (e.g. metal, oxide, etc.)?	Nd+Pr phase is the main magnetic phase in Nd+Pr magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Nd+Pr phase is the main magnetic phase in Nd+Pr magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Nd+Pr phase is the main magnetic phase in Nd+Pr magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Nd+Pr phase is the main magnetic phase in Nd+Pr magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Nd+Pr phase is the main magnetic phase in Nd+Pr magnets. It is a metallic intermetallic compound.	Carbon material	Metal alloy	Sulfated Ti powder	Gallium arsenide or gallium nitride	Antimony trioxide (ATO)	Metal alloy	Metal alloy	Metal or ceramics	Metal or ceramics	W wire filaments	Metal alloy	
23 Product and/or component collection (collection and return rates)	How high are the collection and return rates? Why are they high/low?	Large speakers or speakers in products like laptops, monitors, etc. are usually returned to WEEE collection points. Products with small motors such as electric toothbrushes or shavers might be lost in MSW. Waste generated is lower than PCR.	Products with large motors are usually returned to WEEE collection points. Products with small motors such as electric toothbrushes or shavers might be lost in MSW.	The collection rates of HDDs are high, recycling rates are 90%.	The collection rates of HDDs are high, recycling rates are 90%.	Depends on the product/device	Large speakers or speakers in products like laptops, monitors, etc. are usually returned to WEEE collection points. Small speakers such as in small headphones might be lost in MSW. Waste generated is lower than PCR.	Small quantities of ferrite magnets and ferrite magnet type Nd+Pr magnets are not highly disrupted.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	
24 Current waste generated	Which waste quantities are currently generated?	Waste generated is lower than PCR.	Waste generated is lower than PCR.	HDD waste is not a major waste flow. However, as HDDs are removed from devices, this waste flow concentrates Nd+Pr magnets.	HDD waste is not a major waste flow. However, as HDDs are removed from devices, this waste flow concentrates Nd+Pr magnets.	No information	Waste generated is lower than PCR.	Small quantities of ferrite magnets and ferrite magnet type Nd+Pr magnets are not highly disrupted.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	According to interviews with recyclers, the amount of PCBs per tonne of WEEE has decreased, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	

target CRM	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Dy	Ga	Ba and Sr	Sm + Co	Ta	Ga	Sb	Sb	Sn	Ag, Au, Pd	Co	Sc	W	Cu
application/waste flow	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in speakers	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in motors	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in HDD	additive to Nd+Pr magnets for heat resistance	as a minor additive in Nd+Pr permanent magnets	Ferrite permanent magnets in sensors/relays used	Samarium Cobalt permanent magnets in sensors	in capacitors on PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors on PCBs	flame retardant in PCB resin	in PCB adders	in PCB adders	connectors, contacts, pins, and plating in PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors on PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors, thin film applications in PCBs	electron emitter in integrated circuits in PCB	contacts and connectors in PCBs
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole HDD, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	Ta capacitors remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Ta mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	Ga ICs remain on PCBs separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Ga mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sn mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sn mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the devices and the whole product gets mechanically treated. Ag, Au, and Pd can get disposed in dust fraction. PCB parts end up in Cu-rich fraction which goes to Cu smelter afterwards, or different plastic or residue fractions which go to incineration. Ag, Au, Pd end up in the metal phase as impurity in incineration bottom ash (Eckweert et al., 2020)	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Co mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sc mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually dismantled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, W mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the devices and the whole product gets mechanically treated. In a different plastic or residue fraction, Cu remains after incineration in bottom ash. For fraction without further separation
Potentially existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery process chain including leaching, reduction, solvent extraction, precipitation, and calcination to recover REE and Ga. Ga recovery requires an additional separation step from the leaching solution (Jin et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery (Beja et al., 2024; Bolero et al., 2017)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	selective removal of PCBs with additional manual or automated removal of Ta capacitors from PCBs or molten metal or salt pyrolysis process for liberating Ta capacitors. capacitor waste can be treated by thermal and hydrometallurgical recycling (Eberschaar et al., 2017a; Eberschaar et al., 2017b; European Commission, 2016; Flewter et al., 2019)	removal of Ga ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Ga recovery from concentrates (Eberschaar et al., 2017a; European Commission, 2016; Flewter et al., 2019)	dismantled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sb recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelstein, 2004). 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Tange, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023)	dismantled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sn recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelstein, 2004). 40%-70% of Sn can be recovered (Mark & Tange, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023)	dismantled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electrorefining from Cu anode slimes (KAS) (Hagelstein, 2004) (Eckweert et al., 2019)	theoretical scenario removal of Co-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Co recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of Sc-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Sc recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of W ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with W recovery from concentrates	material in integrated Cu smelters where Cu is recovered	PCBs or parts of PCBs are used as input material or parts of PCBs are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Cu is recovered
Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?																
15	Future waste generated	Which waste quantities are expected to be generated in the future?	The quantity of speaker waste generation is expected to remain stable.	The quantity of motor waste generation is expected to remain stable.	HDD waste generation will likely be lower in the future as HDDs are more and more replaced by SSDs without permanent magnets. But for data centres and professional IEE they are still in use. It is a big driver for spinning disk consumption.	HDD waste generation will likely be lower in the future as HDDs are more and more replaced by SSDs without permanent magnets. But for data centres and professional IEE they are still in use.	No information	The quantity of speaker waste generation is expected to remain stable.	Expected to increase in the future as more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.	More electrified and smart products will lead to an increase in PCBs. Additionally, more and more products include a control panel with a PCB in the background. On the contrary, improved separation and the rise of smart and more complex products result in smaller PCBs which on the other hand contain more intricate components.
31	Availability of identification technology for CRM containing application/material/component/product	Is there a technology to identify the CRM containing application/material/component/product?	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Depends on the product/device	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Magnets can usually be identified visually. However, identification of magnet type is difficult. A rough idea can be derived from the coating as ferrite magnets are often not coated and Nd+Pr magnets are. Exact composition can only be detected by XRF technology after demagnetisation.	Ta capacitors on PCBs can be identified visually, however once get smaller and harder to identify.	Ga and Ga IC can be manually removed from separated PCB, but only few per device.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.	PCBs can be identified visually during dismantling and based on colour after liberation and size reduction.
32	Manual removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Is it possible to manually remove the CRM containing application/material from the product/waste flow (i.e. screened, glued, welded)?	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from speakers is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility is low due to small magnets and glue/epoxy etc.	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from motors is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility increases for larger motors and glue/epoxy etc.	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from HDDs is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility is high as HDDs are already dismantled and the removal of the magnet would be just an additional step.	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from HDDs is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility is high as HDDs are already dismantled and the removal of the magnet would be just an additional step.	Depends on the product/device	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from speakers is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility is low due to small magnets and glue/epoxy etc.	Manual disassembly of permanent magnets from speakers is theoretically possible, but not largely applied. Feasibility is low due to small magnets and glue/epoxy etc.	Ta capacitors can be manually removed from separated PCB, but only few per device.	Ga and Ga IC can be manually removed from separated PCB, but only few per device.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.	PCBs can be removed manually during dismantling, more difficult for smaller PCBs.
33	Automated removability of CRM containing application/material/component (selective removal)	Are processes available to remove the CRM containing application/material from the product/waste flow (i.e. screened, glued, welded)?	Ongoing research and trials regarding automated disassembly of devices, e.g. (Dias et al., 2023).	Ongoing research and trials regarding automated disassembly of devices, Happonen & Fletcher (2023) focusing on autonomous disassembly of permanent magnet motors.	Ongoing research and trials regarding automated disassembly of devices, Burkhardt et al. (2024) focusing on permanent magnet removal from HDDs.	Ongoing research and trials regarding automated disassembly of devices, Burkhardt et al. (2024) focusing on permanent magnet removal from HDDs.	Depends on the product/device	Ongoing research and trials regarding automated disassembly of devices, e.g. (Dias et al., 2023).	Automated disassembly is difficult as the magnets are very small and glued or over-molded.	Selective automated component removal from PCBs only possible for very standardized PCBs. Technologies for semi-automated disassembly of electrical components on PCBs (surface-mounted to concentrate CRM-rich fractions for further hydrometallurgical recovery remove all components together which then need to be sorted (Halem, n.d.; Kaan Automation, 2023; Kozack, 2016; Li et al., 2021). Automatic removal of Ta capacitors is described by Mambo et al. (2023). Another option is thermal PCB pretreatment (molten metal or salt pyrolysis process) for liberation of Ta capacitors followed by mechanical separation (Redwald et al., 2022).	Selective automated component removal from PCBs only possible for very standardized PCBs. Technologies for semi-automated disassembly of electrical components on PCBs (surface-mounted to concentrate CRM-rich fractions for further hydrometallurgical recovery remove all components together which then need to be sorted (Halem, n.d.; Kaan Automation, 2023; Kozack, 2016; Li et al., 2021).	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.	PCBs can be identified by colour and image recognition.
34	Identifiability and separability of CRM containing material after liberation	Is it possible to identify and sort the CRM containing materials after liberation (e.g. shredding)? This can be without preceding removing/liberating or after preceding removal.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	Depends on the product/device	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	Surface-mounted Ta capacitors have characteristic colours and shapes (yellow tantalum and black tantalum) and are thus identifiable e.g. with image recognition.	Ga-containing ICs should be removed before shredding for targeted recovery.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.	PCBs can be identified and sorted by colour and image recognition after liberation, yield losses may occur.
35	Ability to concentrate CRM containing material/mechanically remove impurities	Is it possible to concentrate or to mechanically remove impurities from the CRM containing material flow?	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	Depends on the product/device	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	This is only relevant in case of prior concentration of a permanent magnet containing fraction. Due to the magnetic properties, it is difficult to separate permanent magnets from other magnetic ferrous metals.	(Redwald et al., 2022) demonstrated concentration of surface-mounted Ta capacitors after pyrolysis.	Ga-containing ICs should be removed before shredding for targeted recovery.	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible	Not possible
36	Ability to thermally and/or chemically separate and refine CRMs from concentrates	What is a TRL level?	Different long-loop recycling technologies for refining REE are available (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/leaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short loop recycling technologies like smelting/trip-casting, hydrogen deoxygenation, HCDR, and melt-spinning are used. (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	Different long-loop recycling technologies for refining REE are available (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/leaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short loop recycling technologies like smelting/trip-casting, hydrogen deoxygenation, HCDR, and melt-spinning are used. (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	Different long-loop recycling technologies for refining REE are available (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/leaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short loop recycling technologies like smelting/trip-casting, hydrogen deoxygenation, HCDR, and melt-spinning are used. (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	Different long-loop recycling technologies for refining REE are available (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/leaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short loop recycling technologies like smelting/trip-casting, hydrogen deoxygenation, HCDR, and melt-spinning are used. (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	Depends on the product/device	Different long-loop recycling technologies for refining REE are available (liquid-liquid extraction, selective precipitation/leaching, liquid metal extraction, slagging). In case of short loop recycling technologies like smelting/trip-casting, hydrogen deoxygenation, HCDR, and melt-spinning are used. (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	Different hydro- and solvometallurgical recovery methods were investigated, e.g. by Enli-Kaya et al. (2024) or Papadimitrakou et al. (2024).	Ta capacitor waste can be treated by thermal and hydrometallurgical recycling (Eberschaar et al., 2017a; Redwald et al., 2022; Marito et al., 2023)	Currently recovery of Ga from PCBs (lower SCREEM CRM, but others, 2023), see also TRL research studies demonstrated hydrometallurgical Ga recovery from concentrates (Eberschaar et al., 2017b; European Commission, 2016; Halem et al., 2019)	Sb can be recovered with integrated Cu smelters (Hagelstein, 2004). 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Tange, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023).	Sb can be recovered with integrated Cu smelters (Hagelstein, 2004). 40%-70% of Sn can be recovered (Mark & Tange, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023)	Furthermore, there are different leaching methods. (Chik & Paganter, 2024)	Furthermore, there are different leaching methods. (Chik & Paganter, 2024)	Furthermore, there are different leaching methods. (Chik & Paganter, 2024)	Furthermore, there are different leaching methods. (Chik & Paganter, 2024)

target CRM	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Dy	Ga	Ba and Sr	Sm + Co	Ta	Ga	Sb	Sb	Sn	Ag, Au, Pd	Cu	Sc	W	Cu			
application/waste flow	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in speakers	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in motors	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in HDD	additive to Nd+Pr magnets for heat resistance	as a minor additive in Nd+Pr permanent magnets	Ferrite permanent magnets in speakers/televsion	Samarium Cobalt permanent magnets in sensors (rare permanent)	in capacitors on PCBs	Integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors in PCBs	Flame retardant in PCB resin	in PCB solders	in PCB solders	connectors, contacts, pins, and plating in PCBs	Integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors in PCBs	Integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors in PCBs	electron emitter in integrated circuits in PCB	contacts and connectors in PCBs			
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole HDD, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in ferrous fraction after magnetic separation	Ta capacitors remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Ta mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	Go ICs remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Go mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sn mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the device and the whole product gets mechanically treated. Ag, Au, and Pd get disposed in dust fraction. PCB parts end up in Cu-rich fraction which goes to Cu smelter afterwards, or different plastic and residue fractions which go to incineration. Ag, Au, Pd end up in the metal phase as impurity or incineration bottom ash (Eckowicz et al., 2020)	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Cu mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sc mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter, some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, W mostly ends up in slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the device and the whole product gets mechanically treated. PCB parts end up in different plastic or residue fractions. Cu remains after incineration in bottom ash, for fraction without further separation			
Potentially existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schofield et al., 2024) dismantling probability depends on size of magnet and its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets from smartphones/headphones get dismantled is low	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schofield et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schofield et al., 2024) if a data shredder is involved, magnet recovery is possible after shredding	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schofield et al., 2024) dismantling probability depends on size of magnet and its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets and magnets on PCBs get dismantled is low functional Dy recycling in short loop recycling only for larger and standardized magnet flows	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery (Bajaj et al., 2024; Dolan et al., 2007)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery (Bajaj et al., 2024; Dolan et al., 2007)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material or element recovery (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schofield et al., 2024) dismantling probability in general depends on size of magnet, its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets and magnets on PCBs get dismantled is low the specific removal of Sm/Co depends on the identifiability of magnet material	selective removal of PCBs with Ta capacitors from PCBs or molten metal or salt pyrolysis process for liberating Ta capacitors capacitor waste can be treated by thermal and hydrometallurgical recycling (Eckowicz et al., 2017a; Weidenfeld et al., 2012; Moritz et al., 2023)	removal of Ga ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Ga recovery from concentrates (Eckowicz et al., 2017b; European Commission, 2016; Fievet et al., 2019)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sb recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelstein, 2004). 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Torge, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Sn can be recovered (Hagelstein, 2004)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Sn can be recovered (Hagelstein, 2004)	IFPCBs are not removed from the device and the whole product gets mechanically treated. Ag, Au, and Pd get disposed in dust fraction. PCB parts end up in Cu-rich fraction which goes to Cu smelter afterwards, or different plastic and residue fractions which go to incineration. Ag, Au, Pd end up in the metal phase as impurity or incineration bottom ash (Eckowicz et al., 2020)	theoretical scenario removal of Cu-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Cu recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of Sc-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Sc recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with W recovery from concentrates	PCBs or parts of PCBs are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Cu is recovered Cu is also recovered when PCBs are not disassembled and Cu parts are removed from a shredded waste flow Cu can be recovered from PWB bottom ash by advanced bottom ash processing			
Criteria affecting recoverability	How to evaluate the criteria? Is there a recycling conflict with hazardous substances? Are there hazardous substances in the respective application/waste flow? Will there be hazardous substances liberated during the recovery process? Can the hazardous substances be contained adequately?		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)		Metallic coatings such as nickel can be removed using mechanical, pyrometallurgical, or hydrometallurgical methods, with no technical limitations or conflicts associated with these approaches (Orlitzky et al., 2019)			
5.4 Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No			
5.5 Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the 2CRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.		Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered Nd+Pr powders have lower impacts than primary powders for almost all impact categories (van Nellen et al., 2024). No comparisons for REE extraction known.	
Legal criteria	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?		No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No			
6.1 Recovery targets	No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No			
6.2 Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM-containing application?		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, speakers are not among these products.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, HDDs are not among these products.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.		CRM act requires information regarding removal of the permanent magnet on the label which will be required by 2026 for certain products. However, many products are not mentioned.	
6.3 Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes the majority of magnets in speakers.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in HDDs.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in HDDs.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in speakers.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in sensors.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in sensors.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in sensors.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in sensors.		If considered as strategic project under the CRM Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRM Act can act as incentive for recycling projects. The requirements in the CRM Act regarding recycled content are only for permanent magnets over 0.2 kg which excludes magnets in sensors.	
6.4 End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for 2CRM?		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.		There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concentrates yet.			
6.4 End-of-waste criteria	No		No		No		No		No		No		No		No		Copper Strip Regulation			

target CRM	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Nd + Pr	Dy	Ga	Ba and Sr	Sm + Co	Ta	Ga	Sb	Sb	Sn	Ag, Au, Pd	Co	Sc	W	Cu
application/waste flow	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in speakers	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in motors	Nd+Pr permanent magnets in HDD	additive to Nd+Pr magnets for heat resistance	as a minor additive in Nd+Pr permanent magnets	Ferrite permanent magnets in speakers/televi-vid	Samarium Cobalt permanent magnets in sensors (rare permanent)	in capacitors on PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors in PCBs	flame retardant in PCB resin	in PCB solders	in PCB solders	connectors, contacts, pins, and plating in PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors in PCBs	integrated circuits (ICs) and semiconductors, thin film applications in PCBs	electron emitter in integrated circuits in PCB	contacts and connectors in PCBs
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole HDD, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	no dismantling of the magnet, magnet gets shredded with the whole product or as part of a bigger component, magnet material ends, mostly not liberated up in furnace fraction after magnetic separation	Ta capacitors remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Ta mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	ICs remain on PCBs, separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to integrated smelter. Ga mostly ends up in the slag phase, due to low mass fraction refining not possible	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sb mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sn mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sn mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the devices and the whole product gets mechanically treated. Ag, Au, and Pd can get disposed in dust fraction. PCB parts end up in Cu-rich fraction which goes to Cu smelter afterwards, or different plastic and residue fractions which go to incineration. Ag, Au, Pd end up in the metal phase as impurity or incineration bottom ash (Khanzadeh et al., 2020)	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Co mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, Sc mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	separated PCBs - manually disassembled or separated after shredding - go to Cu smelter; some PCB parts end up in other residues going to incineration afterwards, W mostly ends up slag phase or incineration bottom ash	IFPCBs are not removed from the devices and the whole product gets mechanically treated. PCB parts end up in different plastic or residue fractions. Cu remains after incineration in bottom ash; fine fraction without further separation
Potentially existing or potential End treatment scenario with CRM recovery	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024) dismantling probability depends on size of magnet and its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets from smartphones/headphones get dismantled is low	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop recycling) or element recovery (long loop recycling) (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Schoenfeld et al., 2024) dismantling probability depends on size of magnet and its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets and magnets on PCBs get dismantled is low functional Dy recycling in short loop recycling only for larger and standardized magnet flows	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for element recovery process chain including leaching, reduction, solvent extraction, precipitation, and calcination to recover REE and Ga; Ga recovery requires an additional separation step from the leaching solution (Zin et al., 2024)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material recovery (Benja et al., 2024; Boleen et al., 2027)	dismantling and separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material or element recovery (quality requirements for element recovery lower than for material recovery) (Skan Recycling, 2025) dismantling probability in general depends on size of magnet, its accessibility, i.e. the likelihood that small magnets and magnets on PCBs get dismantled is low the specific removal of Sm/Co magnets depends on the identifiability of magnet material	selective removal of PCBs with additional manual or automated removal of Ta capacitors from PCBs or molten metal or salt pyrolysis process for liberating Ta capacitors capacitor waste can be treated by thermal and hydrometallurgical recycling (Kebeschauer et al., 2017a; Weidenfeld et al., 2022; Morlock et al., 2023)	removal of Ga ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Cu recovery from concentrates (Kebeschauer et al., 2017b; European Commission, 2016; Flewter et al., 2019)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters with dedicated Sb recovery as a by-product from lead refining (Hagelüken, 2004), 40%-70% of Sb can be recovered (Mark & Torge, 2006; Mark & Lehner, 2023) Hydrometallurgical separation after separation from Cu phase (Barragan et al., 2020)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Sn can be recovered (Hagelüken, 2004)	disassembled PCBs or whole products with high value PCBs (such as smartphones, tablets, etc.) are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Ag, Au, and Pd can be recovered by electro-winning from Cu anode slimes (KAS) (Hagelüken, 2004) (Khanzadeh et al., 2009)	theoretical scenario removal of Co-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Cu recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of Sc-containing ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with Sc recovery from concentrates	theoretical scenario removal of ICs from PCBs, hydrometallurgical treatment with W recovery from concentrates	PCBs or parts of PCBs are used as input material in integrated Cu smelters where Cu is recovered Cu is also recovered when PCBs are not disassembled and Cu parts are removed from a shredded waste flow Cu could be recovered from PCBs bottom ash by advanced bottom ash processing	

Nb.	Criteria (affecting recoverability)	How to evaluate the criteria?
1	Uberschauer et al., 2020% Uberschauer, 2017c van Nieren et al., 2014 W. Li et al., 2021 Wang et al., 2024 X. Li et al., 2022 X. Li et al., 2023 Xiu et al., 2015 Yang et al., 2013 Yu, 2021 Zhang et al., 2015	Uberschauer, M., Chen, S. J., & Ritter, V. S. (2017). Challenges for critical raw material recovery from WEEE – The case study of gallium. Waste Management, 60, 534–545. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2016.12.035 Uberschauer, Maximilian (2017). Assessing recycling strategies for critical raw materials in waste electrical and electronic equipment, Institut für Technischen Umweltschutz, ITU-Schriftenreihe 35, Technische Universität Berlin, https://doi.org/10.14279/depositonce-6156 van Nieren, S. S., Miranda Nicotencati, B., Tukker, A., & Kleijn, R. (2014). Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling: Progressing towards sustainable industrial-scale technology. Journal of Cleaner Production, 458, 142453. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2014.142453 Li, W., Edders, B., & Brier, M. (2021). SHD implementation for Automated PCB Recycling. In Institute of Imaging and Computer Vision, RWTH Aachen University (Journal article) https://www.its.rwth-aachen.de/bitstream/handle/10181/38888/1/SHD.pdf Wang, L., Liang, D., Yu, R., Wang, M., Tian, Y., Ma, T., Yang, B., Xu, B., & Jiang, W. (2024). Progress and prospects in magnesium alloy scrap recycling. Journal of Magnesium and Alloys, https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jma.2024.11.031 Li, X., Ma, B., Hu, D., Zhao, D., Chen, Y., & Wang, C. (2022). Efficient separation and purification of indium and gallium in spent Copper indium gallium di-selenide (CIGS). Journal of Cleaner Production, 339, 130458. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.130458 Li, X., Ma, B., Wang, C., Hu, D., Liu, Y., & Chen, Y. (2023). Recycling and recovery of spent copper–indium–gallium–di-selenide (CIGS) solar cells: A review. International Journal of Minerals, Metallurgy and Materials, 30(16), 989–1002. https://doi.org/10.1007/s12413-022-1552-Y/NETRCS Xiu, F., Qi, Y., & Zhang, F. (2015). Leaching of Au, Ag, and Pd from waste printed circuit boards of mobile phone by iodide lixiviant after supercritical water pre-treatment. Waste Management, 41, 134–141. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2015.02.020 Yang, F., Kubota, F., Bala, Y., Kamrta, H., & Guo, H. (2013). Selective extraction and recovery of rare earth metals from phosphor powders in waste fluorescent lamps using an ionic liquid system. Journal of Hazardous Materials, 254–255, 79–88. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.03.026 Yu, R. (2023). What are heat sinks and how are they made? Rapid Prototyping & Low Volume Production. https://www.bergomachinery.com/what-are-heat-sinks-and-how-are-they-made/ Zhang, X., Guan, Y., Yan, X., Yuan, H., Xu, J., Guo, J., Zhou, Y., Su, R., & Guo, Z. (2015). Selective Dissolving Separation of Tin-Lead Alloy for Dismantling of Electronic Components from Printed Circuit Boards. ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering, 3(8), 1696–1700. https://doi.org/10.1021/acsuschemeng.5b00136
2	CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 Copper Scrap Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 CRM Act (EU) 2024/1252 ESPR (EU) 2024/1781 Glass Cullet Regulation (EU) No 179/2012 Metal Scrap Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 POP-Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 WEEE Directive 2012/19/EU	Regulation (EC) 1272/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 December 2008 on classification, labelling, and packaging of substances and mixtures Commission Regulation (EU) No 715/2013 of 25 July 2013 establishing criteria determining when copper scrap ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Regulation (EU) 2024/1252 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 April 2024 establishing a framework for ensuring a secure and sustainable supply of critical raw materials and amending Regulations (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/7724 and (EU) 2019/1020 Regulation (EU) 2024/1781 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for sustainable products, amending Directive (EU) 2020/1828 and Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 and repealing Directive 2009/125/EC Commission Regulation (EU) No 179/2012 of 10 December 2012 establishing criteria determining when glass cullet ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Council Regulation (EU) No 333/2011 of 30 March 2011 establishing criteria determining when certain types of scrap metal ceases to be waste under Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1021 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 June 2019 on persistent organic pollutants (POPs) Directive 2012/19/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) (recast)

Abbreviations used

ATO	Antimony trioxide
BFR	Brominated flame retardant
CCFL	Cold Cathode Fluorescent Lamp
COG	Cu-Indium-Gallium-Selenide
CRM	Critical Raw Material
CRT	Cathode Ray Tube
DPP	Digital Product Passport
EoL	End-of-life
EU	European Union
FL	Fluorescent Lamp
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
LCD	Liquid-crystal display
LED	Light-emitting diode
LIRS	Laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
NIR	Near-infrared
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
REE	Rare Earth Elements
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
XRF	X-ray fluorescence
XRT	X-ray transmission